

Synchronal Toughening and in situ Self-healing of Laminated Fiber-reinforced Composites via Copolymer Interlayers

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Outline

- Motivation / Background
- 3D-printing and Composite Fabrication
- Investigation of Toughened / Self-healing Composites
 - In-plane Tensile Comparison
 - Thermo-mechanical Property Evaluation
 - Interlaminar Fracture Toughening
 - *In Situ* Self-healing via Thermal Remending
- Summary / Conclusions

Motivation

Aerospace

Automotive

Naval

Civil

Energy

Motivation/Background

Composite architecture

Compos. Struct. **79** (2007)

Difficult to inspect/repair

www.dsto.defence.gov.au

Proactive Toughening to Prevent Delamination

Polym. Chem. **4** (2013)

Reactive Self-healing to Address Delamination

Capsule

Vascular

Intrinsic

Annu. Rev. Mater. Res. **40** (2010)

Fracture damage

ASM International (2010) *Polymer* **53** (2012)

Catastrophic failure

USAF Hilltop Times

Soft Materials

Angew. Chem. **51** (2012)

Structural Materials

Science **295** (2002)

- Interfacial contact enables room-temperature repair
- Requires external energy for repair (e.g., elevated temperature)

Thermal Remending

- **Thermal remending** is a hybrid (extrinsic-intrinsic) technique with **thermoplastic inclusions** embedded in **structural material**
- After damage, application of **heat** enables the **bond reformation** of thermoplastic to provide healing of the larger structural host
- Poly(ethylene-co-methacrylic acid) – **EMAA** – is a commodity polymer with proven **thermal remending** ability

Modified Matrices

Polymer 92 (2016)

ACS Appl. Mater. Inter. 1 (2009)

Particles and Woven Fibers

Compos. Part A 43 (2012)

Interlayers

Macromol. Mater. Eng. 295 (2010)

Compos. Part A 43 (2012)

Important Notes

1. Healing achieved **ex situ** - (in an oven)
2. Healing requires heating **above the glass-transition** temperature (T_g) - (softening)

Toughening
+
Self-healing

State-of-the-Art Thermal Remending Technique

- Recently our lab has developed a thermal remending platform for *in situ* self-healing below the glass-transition temperature (T_g)

3D-printing onto preform substrate

Pristine multifunctional composite laminate

Internal delamination damage

Self-healing via *in situ* thermal remending

Textile Resistive Heaters

3D-Printing and Composite Fabrication

- Investigate effect of EMAA pattern **thickness**, **areal coverage**, and **orientation** on toughening and healing performance
- Fused deposition modeling (FDM) to precisely print EMAA patterns directly onto woven substrate

t – pattern thickness S – pattern spacing W – trace width

Printing directly on woven fabric

Completed prints with high precision

VARTM Process and Composite Fabrication

EMAA Toughened GFRP layup

$[90/0]_4/EMAA/[90/0]_4$

Self-healing GFRP layup

$[0/90]_2/H/0/90/0/EMAA/90/0/90/H/[0/90]_2$

GFRP – Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer

Laminated Composite Full Thickness CT Scan

Curing conditions: 24h @ RT + 2h @ 121°C + 2h @ 150°C

In-plane Tensile Performance

- EMAAs inclusions have **minimal impact** on **in-plane tensile** performance

Note

- EMAAs at maximum 36% areal coverage

- Bilinear stress vs. strain response is nearly **indistinguishable** between EMAAs toughened and plain composites
- Initial modulus, final modulus, and ultimate tensile strength exhibit **<5% difference**

Thermomechanical Characterization

- EMAAs inclusions have **minimal impact** on **thermomechanical performance**

DMA Fixture & Specimen

3-pt Flexure (1Hz, 5°C/min)

Dynamic Thermo-mechanical Flexural Behavior

Elastic (Storage) Modulus Comparison

$$E^* = E' + iE'' \quad \tan(\delta) = \frac{E''}{E'}$$

ASTM D-7028, E-1640

- Evolution of E', E'', and tan(δ) are nearly **indistinguishable** between EMAA toughened and plain composites
- Elastic storage modulus exhibit **<5% difference** at room temperature and the glass transition temperature

Because thermal remending (130°C) occurs below the T_g of the composite matrix:

- Maintain **structural integrity** during healing
- EMAAs inclusions **do not meaningfully affect** thermomechanical performance within operating temperature range

Fracture Testing and *In Situ* Thermal Remending

- **Mode-I fracture** testing is used to characterize **toughening** and **self-healing** performance

Fracture Testing to Evaluate Interlaminar Toughness

Double Cantilever Beam (DCB)

ASTM D5528

Backlight

Thermal Remending to Evaluate Self-healing Performance

In Situ Heating

Heating Cycle: (heat) 15 min. @ 130°C (cool) 30 min. until RT

Critical Strain Energy Release Rate

Fracture Resistance (R-curve)

Modified Beam Theory (Eq. 1)

$$G_{IC} = \frac{3P\hat{\delta}}{2b(a + |\Delta|)}$$

a = total crack length ($a_0 + \Delta a$)

$|\Delta|$ = fixed end correction factor*

Area Method** (Eq. 2)

$$G_{IC} = \frac{1}{b} \frac{\Delta U}{\Delta a} \quad \Delta U = \int_0^{\hat{\delta}} P d\hat{\delta} \Big|_{\Delta a}$$

Load vs. Displacement

Healing Efficiency** (Eq. 3)

$$\hat{\eta} = \frac{G_{IC}^{healed}}{G_{IC}^{virgin}} \times 100\%$$

G_{IC} calculated with area method

*Journal of Materials Science Letters 8 (1989).

** Advanced Materials 26 (2014).

Interlaminar Toughening Performance

- **Areal coverage and thickness** dominates **global** toughening while **orientation** controls **local** crack propagation behavior

- Up to **450%** increase in interlaminar fracture resistance!
- L vs. T less pronounced at higher areal coverages

In situ Self-healing via Thermal Remending

Self-healing GFRP layout
 $[0/90]_2/H/0/90/0/EMAA/90/0/90/H/[0/90]_2$

- Up to 100% healing efficiency is achieved for 10 heal cycles where EMAA pattern areal coverage dominates healing response

Healing Cycle: (heat) 15 min. @ 130°C (cool) 30 min. until RT

Scanning Electron Microscope Images

main scale = $25\mu\text{m}$, inset scale = $10\mu\text{m}$

- Cohesive fracture shows signs of **ductile tearing**
- Micro-porous networks** form after Heal 1
- Micro-porous networks** are fully developed by Heal 10

Summary / Future Work

- Designed a proactive **toughening** and reactive **healing** strategy to mitigate **delamination**.
- Achieved up to a **450% increase** in mode-I fracture resistance via incorporation of **3D-printed EMAA interlayers**.
- Minimal (< **5%**) effect of interlayer modifications on **in-plane tensile** and **thermomechanical** performance compared to plain composite laminates.
- Demonstrated repeated complete (**100%**) **restoration** of fracture resistance for **10 consecutive heal cycles** without degradation in healing performance.
- Discovered EMAA **areal coverage** and **thickness** dominates the **global** fracture and self-repair response while interlayer pattern **orientation** controls **local** crack propagation behavior.

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